

AWARENESS AND PRACTICE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG UNIVERSITY OF JOS FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES

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ABSTRACT

Several researchers have reported on cervical cancer screening. The screening influences the incidence and prognosis of cervical cancer. The knowledge of people on this screening have been said to influence practice. This research therefore sorts to assess the knowledge and practice of the student population in the University of Jos. A sample size of 120 was selected from the population of study. A descriptive survey design was used to assess the knowledge and practice of respondents and the findings were illustrated and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. The researchers among other findings found out that only 33.04% have ever heard of Pap smear, among which only about 55.10% related it cervical cancer. Only 7.89% knew the recommended age for the screening and only 10.53% were aware of the frequency. Among the respondents only 13.91% have ever done Pap smear, with a whopping 78.26% saying they have never done the test. Out of those who have ever done the test only 25% had done it more than once. The relationship between knowledge and practice was significant, indicating that knowledge influenced practice.

KEYWORDS: Cervical cancer, Pap smear, Developed and developing countries, University of Jos, Nigeria

Received for Publication: 23/01/14

Accepted for Publication: 22/03/14

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INTRODUCTION

The inequity between developed and developing countries has multiple sources. The burden of the disease in many developing countries is often overshadowed and misplaced by other health priorities such as HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria etc., this has resulted in the displacement of health policies that that might be geared towards implementation of effective prevention programs such as cervical screening. Also, new and effective strategies for screening and treating precancerous lesions are not widespread, having very few programs offering relatively comprehensive services. Occasionally, they may be opportunistic if incorporated in family planning services, or may be linked to research studies (Sherris *et al*, 1993). Furthermore, health resources are focused on well-established health programs targeting areas such as pregnant and lactating women, and children younger than 5 years of age (Bishop *et al*, 1995).

A policy to provide women over the age of 30 years with three (3) free Pap smears, 10 years apart, has not been successfully implemented (ACCP, 2004).

A study on examining the beliefs and Pap test utilization among Chinese American women, the largest Asian female population in the United States, 86% reported having a Pap test within the prior 3 years (Lee-lin *et al*, 2007).

Mangoma, Chirenje, Chimbari and Chandiwana (2006), in a study of sociological and anthropological insights into the Zimbabwean rural women's perceptions and understanding of cervical cancer screening, 95.78% of the 356 women from Mutoka and Shurugwi districts that were interviewed, had never gone for the screening and had little knowledge about the disease in terms of causes, prevention and treatment.

In a study in Botswana to explore knowledge and beliefs of 30 women (recruited from all income levels) about cervical cancer and its screening, it was found that knowledge of cervical cancer and Pap smear tests was inadequate among women with low incomes. Pap smear utilization was also limited among low income women. Of the 18 who had at least one Pap smear test in their lifetime, 8 (44%) had opportunistic screening as a result of having gynecological symptoms. 12 women (40%) had never had Pap smear test. Major barriers to Pap smear screening included inadequate knowledge about Pap smear testing, providers' negative attitudes, and limited access to doctors (McFarland, 2003).

The current wisdom about cervical cancer control is the critical importance of early detection. However, most of the women in developing nations present with advanced disease when nothing can be done for them (Adewole, 2005).

Studies in Uganda aimed at better understanding factors that influence usage of available reproductive healthcare services and how they would relate to cervical cancer screening, identified barriers to include ignorance about cervical cancer, cultural constructs about the illness, economic factors, domestic gender power relations, alternative authoritative sources of reproductive health knowledge, and unfriendly healthcare services (Mutyaba, Faxelid, Mirembe and Weiderpass, 2007).

A study in Owerri discovered a very low level of uptake. Most common reasons given for not doing the Pap test were lack of awareness; 390 (46.1%), no need for it; 106 (12.5%), while 98 (11.6%) were afraid of a possible bad result (Ezem, 2007).

Despite the existence of evidence-based secondary prevention methods such as Pap smear, cervical cancer kills a disproportionate number of women in developing countries (ACCP, 2004). With the test requiring repeated or routine screenings of women at intervals, developing countries may not have prowess to carry out this model, and as such, may not have the capacity for their health services to organize and sustain such programs.

This study therefore, seeks to assess the female students' awareness and practice of cervical screening, as well as proffer relevant findings and recommendations that will help in curbing the menace posed by cervical cancer.

OBJECTIVES

Specific objectives include to;

- 1 Find out the female undergraduates' attitude towards cervical screening (Pap smear).
- 2 Assess the respondents' practice of Pap smear test

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

It is a quantitative research based on the classification made by Robson in 1993. In more specific terms, the study is a descriptive survey, a non-experimental study design which seeks to assess the female undergraduates' knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening.

LOCATION/AREA OF STUDY

The study setting is University of Jos, situated in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State, within the North-Central geo-political zone of the country.

The university was established in 1971 as a satellite campus of the University of Ibadan. In October 1975, the then military government under General Murtala Mohammed established the University as a separate institution. Existing faculties in the school include Arts and Social Sciences, Education, Environmental Sciences, Law, Management Sciences, Medical sciences, Natural Sciences, and Pharmaceutical Sciences. The University embraces 53 departments, a teaching hospital and several other academic units such as center for continuing education, center for research and development, the information and communication (ICT) directorate, among others.

The institution has two (2) campuses; the temporary site located along Bauchi road and the permanent site situated in Naraguta. The institution has student population as follows;

3. Full time students – 18, 952
4. Part time – 12, 389

The staff population is also as follows;

3. Academic staff – 871
4. Non-academic staff – 1,671

POPULATION OF STUDY

The population of study is the female undergraduates of the institution. This population comprises mainly of young adults who are in different levels of study at their various departments and faculties in the institution.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHINQUES

The study involved about 120 female undergraduates at different levels of study within the various faculties of the University. The method of sampling employed was convenience sampling, cutting across all the faculties of the institution.

INSRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The instrument used for data collection was a semi structured questionnaire which was to be self-administered. Each respondent was asked to fill the questionnaire which is divided into three (3) sections; encompassing their socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge, as well as attitude and practice of cervical screening. The questions asked are simple and clear, and the rating scale used is Thurnstone scale.

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF INSTRUMENT

The study adapted the structural format of an existing questionnaire whose psychometric properties have been established. Researchers proof read the questionnaire thoroughly individually and grey areas were addressed adequately. Pretesting was carried out on a small number of respondents as a trial run for the main research intended.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The instruments for data collection (questionnaire) were distributed to the respondents at their respective lecture halls, library, departmental spots or places of residence based on convenience. The researcher waited to collect the questionnaires from the respondents.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data provided by the respondents were processed and presented using the descriptive method of data analysis from which inferences were drawn. The information was represented using tables as well as frequency tables, percentages, measures of central tendencies. The inferential method was used to test the hypotheses of the research study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Verbal informed consent was obtained from the respondents as regards participation in the study. Opting to participate was a choice as respondents were not coerced. To guarantee anonymity, questions eliciting the respondents' identity were avoided, and all the information provided by respondents was treated with utmost confidence. Also, the researcher attempted answering questions raised by respondents.

RESULTS**Table 1: Showing Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents**

Characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
AGE		
16-20	14	12.17
21-25	61	53.04
26-30	27	23.48
31-35	4	3.48
Above 35	5	4.35
No response	4	3.48
Total	115	100.00
FACULTY		
Arts	19	16.52
Education	14	12.17
Social science	16	13.91
Environmental science	8	6.96
Law	14	12.17
Management sciences	9	7.83
Medical sciences	19	16.52
Pharmacy	7	6.09
Natural science	8	6.96
No response	1	0.90
Total	115	100.00
LEVEL OF STUDY		
100	13	11.30
200	41	35.65
300	31	26.96
400	11	9.57
500	12	10.43
600	1	0.90
No response	6	5.22
Total	115	100.03
MARITAL STATUS		
Married	13	11.30
Single	100	86.96
Separated/divorced	Nil	0.00
Widowed	Nil	0.00
No response	2	1.74
Total	115	100.00

TYPE OF MARRIAGE		
Monogamy	11	84.62
Polygamy	1	7.69
No response	1	7.69
Total	13	100.00
RELIGION		
Christianity	108	93.91
Islam	7	6.09
Others	Nil	0.00
Total	115	100.00
TRIBE		
Hausa	8	6.96
Igbo	23	20.00
Yoruba	13	11.30
Others	66	57.39
No response	5	4.35
Total	115	100.00

Table 1 shows that the mean age of respondents is approximately 24 years, with majority of the respondents; 61 (53.4%) falling within 21-25 years of age, and only a few; 5 (4.35%) being above 35 years of age. These respondents cut across the various faculties of the institution; with Faculties of Arts and Medical Sciences accounting for the highest percentages; 19 (16.52%) each, while pharmacy accounted for the least number of respondents; 7 (6.09%).

Most of the respondents are from 200 and 300 level; 41 (35.65%) and 31 (26.96%) respectively, while only 1 (0.90%) is from 600 level which could be attributable to the fact that only one department (medicine) has that level. Only few are married (11.30%, n=13), majority (86.96%, n=100) are single, while 2 of the respondents (1.74%) did not comment on their marital status. Of the married individuals, 11 (84.62%) are in a monogamous setting, while 1 (7.69%) is from a polygamous home. One did not comment on her type of marital setting.

Considering their system of belief, 108 (93.91%) of them are Christians, while 7 (6.09%) are Muslims, with none being traditional or from other religions of the world. In terms of ethnicity, it is indicative of the fact that those from other ethnic groups, aside the three major ethnic groups of the country, are in the majority; (57.39%, n=66). This is likely associated with the fact that other ethnic groups within the middle belt especially Plateau State, constitute the largest population of undergraduates of the institution.

Table 2: Knowledge of Pap smear Test

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Ever heard of pap smear		
Yes	38	33.04
No	63	54.78
No response	14	12.17
Total	115	99.99
Information source (multiple choice)		
Health practitioner	21	37.50
Friend/relation/colleague	10	17.86
Books/posters/magazine	8	14.29
Lecture/campaign	7	12.50
Media	7	12.50
others	1	1.79
no response	2	3.57

Total	56	100.01
Personal discrimination of pap smear		
Comments	29	76.32
No comments/response	9	23.68
Total	38	100.00
Based on comments made		
Relates to abdominal scan	1	3.45
Relates to reproductive organ	10	34.48
Relates to cancer without any clear cut distinction	2	6.90
Relates to cervical cancer	16	55.17
Total	29	100.00
Pap smear synonym		
Pelvic examination	2	5.26
Cervical screening	17	44.74
Vaginal examination	15	39.47
Don't know	2	5.26
No response	2	5.26
Total	38	99.99
Recommended early age for first pap smear test		
Below 18 years	5	13.16
18-21 years	19	50.00
22-30 years	3	7.89
31-40 years	Nil	-
Above 40 years	Nil	-
Don't know	10	26.32
No response	1	2.63
Total	38	100.00
Recommended pap smear frequency (years)		
Once a year	13	34.21
Once in 2-3 years	4	10.53
Once in 5 years	Nil	-
Once in 10 years	Nil	-
Don't know	20	52.63
No response	1	2.63
Total	38	100.00

Table 2 shows that more of the respondents; 63 (54.78%) are unaware of Pap smear test, with 38 (33.04%) indicating they have ever heard of the test, while 14 (12.17%) of them did not respond to the question.

Sampling from those that have ever heard of the test, 21 (37.50%) indicated health practitioners as their information source, with only 1 (1.79%) having a source other than the ones indicated in the questionnaire options/table (i.e. internet). Based on their personal description of Pap smear, 29 (76.32%) of the respondents commented, with about 16 (55.17%) of them relating the test to cervical cancer, while 10 (34.48%) of them were ambiguous as they only related it to the reproductive system (vagina to be specific). 2 (6.90%) related to cancer without any clear distinction. In addition, a reasonable number (44.74%, n=17) know that Pap smear is synonymous to cervical screening, with 15 (39.47%) misconceiving it to be vaginal examination, while 2 (5.26%) know nothing about its alternate name.

Table 2 also indicates that a greater proportion of the respondents; 19 (50%) thought that it is recommended for women as early as 18-21 years of age. Only 3 (7.89%) knew the recommended age for the first test, with 10 (26.32%) not knowing the recommended age. As regards the frequency of the test, only 4 (10.53%) are aware that the test is to be done once in every 2-3 years. 20 (52.63%) didn't know the recommended frequency of the test.

Table 3: Showing the Distribution of Practice of Pap smear Test among Respondents

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Ever had pap smear test done		
Yes	16	13.91
No	90	78.26
No response	9	7.83
Total	115	100.00
Number of times they have done the test		
Once	12	75.00
Twice	2	12.50
Trice	2	12.50
Total	16	100.00
Age of first test (years)		
17	2	12.50
18	1	6.25
20	2	12.50
21	1	6.25
23	4	25.00
24	3	18.75
27	1	6.25
Can't remember	1	6.25
Total	16	100.00
Year of last pap smear		
< 3 years ago	8	50.00
3-5 years ago	6	37.50
6-10 years ago	2	12.50
>10 years ago	Nil	-
Total	16	100.00
Reasons for doing the test		
Doctors request/recommendation	3	18.75
Subsidized/free	4	25.00
Belief	5	31.25
Part of general screening program	3	18.75
Others	Nil	-
No response	1	6.25
Total	16	100.00
Plan of having next pap		

smear test		
Less than a year	5	31.25
1-2 years' time	4	25.00
3-4 years' time	1	6.25
5 or more years' time	3	18.75
not planning to	Nil	-
others (don't know)	2	12.50
no response	1	6.25
Total	16	100.00

Tables 3 shows that only 16 (13.91%) have ever done the test, while a significant proportion of the study population; 90 (78.26%), have never done the test at any given time. Majority of those who have done the test; 12 (75%) did it once, with only 4 (25%) indicating to have done it multiple times, and the modal age for the test being 23 years.

Half of the respondents who have done the test before, had their last less than 3 years ago, with none appearing to have done her last more than 10 years ago. 31.25% out of this group, did the test because they believe they should do it, with the same number planning to have their next Pap smear in less than a year, while 2 (12.50%) appear not to have made up their mind as regards their plan towards having the test done.

Table 4: Showing the Respondents' Distribution Based on Findings of the Test

Questionnaire item	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Findings of the test		
Normal	14	87.50
Abnormal	1	6.25
No response	1	6.25
Total	16	100.00
Going back for checkup for abnormal results		
Yes	1	100.00
No	0	-
Total	1	100.00
Duration before going back for the check up		
After first dose of medication	1	100.00
Others	Nil	-
Total	1	100.00

In table 4 it shows that the largest population of those who have done the test; 14 (87.50%) knew their test result to be normal. 1 (6.25%) had an abnormal result, but she went back for checkup after her first dose of medication. One did not report the finding of her test.

TESTING OF RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Table 5: Relationship between Knowledge and Practice

Knowledge	Practice		Total
	Positive	Negative	
Yes	16 (A)	22 (B)	38
No	0 (C)	77 (D)	77
Total	16	99	115

$$\text{Calculated } X^2 = 37.66 \text{ df}=1 \text{ p}=0.05$$

Using non directional chi square table for $df=1$, level of significance = 0.05, critical value $=\chi^2\alpha = 3.84$. Since $\chi^2 > \chi^2\alpha$, H_0 is rejected while H_A (alternate hypothesis) is accepted, indicating that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and practice among respondents (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

In this study, a significant number of the study population fell within the age range of 21-30 years. These respondents cut across the various Faculties of the Institution, with Faculties of Arts and Medical Sciences accounting for the highest percentages, while Pharmacy accounted for the least number of respondents. This is similar with the Canadian study on female undergraduates in south-Western Ontario as it cuts across the various faculties of the Institution (Fletcher, 2005). Most of the respondents were from 200 and 300 level. Only few are married with the majority being single.

Awareness of Pap smear test was below average, which is in contrast with high levels of awareness recorded among female university staff and students in Accra, Ghana (Adanu, 2002)

Respondents who were informed via health practitioners were more than those who got there information from lecture/campaign and media. More than half of the respondents were able to relate the test to cervical cancer, with a reasonable percentage relating it to the reproductive system. Just a few related the test to abdominal scan. This implies that less than half do not have a clear cut/distinctive knowledge of the test. This finding agrees with that of Massad, (2006) but in contrasts to that of a German study which indicated that more than half of the respondents considered themselves as insufficiently informed (Klug, 2005). In addition, more than two-third of the respondents who demonstrated awareness on the test knew that Pap smear is synonymous to cervical screening

About half of the respondents said that the recommended age which the first Pap smear test should be done is 18-21 years. This is in line with the ACS's guidelines for the detection of cancer (2011), which states that all women should begin cervical cancer screening about 3 years after they begin having vaginal intercourse, but no later than 21 years old some. European countries also start at age 18.

Only a few knew that the recommended frequency for Pap smear test is every 2-3 years and a little below average of the respondents believed that Pap smear test should be done yearly. This belief is likely based on the previous WHO recommendation, however. However a little above average of the respondents didn't know how frequent the test is supposed to be done. This finding differs with that of Massad, (2005) where majority of the respondents understood that Pap smear test should be repeated at intervals ranging from 1-3 years depending on result finding.

The research findings also indicated that only a few of the total number of respondents had ever done the smear test. However, a higher practice rate was found among female undergraduates of South-Western Ontario, Canada where a little above average of the respondents have practiced Pap smear test (Fletcher, 2005).

The research also revealed that those who have ever done the test have better knowledge than those who had not. This finding is similar to that obtained in Ontario, Canada, in a comparative study of college-aged female students who had had Pap smear and those who had not (Fletcher, 2005). Although the women who had had Pap smear were more knowledgeable about their cervical health, their knowledge was still inadequate.

Out of those who have ever done the test, majority of them did it only once, while very few have had it twice and thrice in their lives. When asked of the age of first test, 23 years stood out, followed by 24 years with one who could remember the age she first did it. Half of them had their last pap smear in less than 3 years ago, followed by 3-5 years ago accounting for, with very few having theirs in about 6-10 years. This portrays the lack of continuity of the

test among respondents who have ever practiced it which is related to the findings of Lee-lin *et al*, (2007) where majority of the respondents did the test at least once 3 years before the study
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Majority of the respondents had a normal result with only one having an abnormal test result, which did go back for a checkup after her first dose of medication. A higher frequency of the respondents who had ever done the test believed that they ought to do the test,

A significant proportion of respondents who have had previous Pap smear test, plan to have their next Pap smear test in less than a year, while those planning towards a year or two constituted one fourth of the population with one eight undecided as to when they plan to have their next pap smear test.

With respect to the hypotheses stated in this research work, it is worthy of note that a significant association exist between knowledge of respondents and their practice of Pap smear test. This lends verisimilitude to the assertion that knowledge about a particular act and its relevance positively influences practice.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the absence of adequate knowledge on cervical cancer screening among respondents which invariable influence the practice of Pap smear test by the respondents. This buttresses the need for intensified enlightenment/sensitization campaigns.

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